

Visual and Multimodal Approaches for Sarcasm Detection: A Review

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Abstract: *The word Sarcasm basically means the use of irony to either mock or convey contempt. It is a linguistic as well as social phenomenon that is not only complex but also means the opposite of what is spoken. Movement of eyebrows, eye gaze patterns, asymmetric smiles and micro expressions are often used while delivering a sarcastic remark. As sarcastic expressions most often mean the opposite of their actual words or visible emotions, the detection of sarcasm is an important area in the field of AI. This paper presents an overview of the existing research carried out in this area. Approaches using machine learning and deep learning techniques with a focus on text as well as emotion and multimodal based approaches have been reviewed in this study. Methods, datasets and key findings of selected papers have been highlighted in this paper. Also the research paper gaps for future works with emphasis on facial and micro-expression analysis, multimodal sarcasm detection and extraction of facial features for sarcasm detection.*

Keywords: *Sarcasm Detection, Facial Expressions, Deep Learning, Emotion Analysis, Multimodal Learning.*

1. Introduction

Sarcasm is an implicit human communication style where the intended meaning of words or expressions deviates from their literal interpretation. It is frequently used in social media online conversations, and everyday conversations. Automated systems have significant difficulties correctly identifying ironic content, but humans are able to do so by analyzing contextual, emotional, and visual clues. In the field of emotional computing, natural language processing and artificial intelligence, the detection of sarcasm has gained importance as research subject [1]. Traditionally, the sentiment analysis methods were mainly dependent upon lexical polarity and syntactic characteristics to categorize opinions as negative or positive. These techniques need not work well in the case of sarcasm, as sarcasm usually makes use of pleasant or neutral language to convey conflicting or negative sentiments [2].

In order to overcome the constraints posted by the traditional methods, researchers have explored several machine learning (ML) and deep learning techniques for detection of sarcasm. To improve the performance of detection, especially in social media settings- Emoji's, hashtags, and punctuation are examples of emotional cues that have been used.

This paper examines the earlier research carried out on sarcasm detection, with focus on the methods that use machine learning and deep learning techniques to study text-based, emotion-based, and multimodal approaches. Important issues and research gaps that inspire the creation of improved deep learning framework for detection of sarcasm based on facial expression have been highlighted.

2. Related Work

Vitman O et. al. proposed a method for sarcasm detection that incorporates emotional characteristics along with contextual data. Their method makes use of mood and emotion models in order to enhance the detection of

sarcasm [3]. Discrimination of irony and sarcasm using transformer-based model was presented by Potamias R.A et.al. It was seen that transformer easily capturing long-range dependencies in text thereby outperforming conventional machine learning models. Though the model performs strongly on textual datasets is lacks visual and facial expressions analysis [4]. Bouazizi and Ohtsuki distinguished sarcasm using a pattern-based method. Criteria to recognize textual sarcastic patterns and linguistic features was used in their approach. Structured text gave a good accuracy, but informal or visually expressive sarcasm was difficult to detect by their method. Farabi S.et al conducted a comprehensive survey on multi-modal that explored methods which combined graphics, text, emoticons as well as music. The authors highlighted the fact that multimodal strategies gave a better result than single modal ones. Some of the difficulties that they faced included intricacy in the model design and availability of limited data [6]. The function of emoji's in the detection of sarcasm was studied by Subramanian J. et al. by their Emoji Sarcasm Detection (ESD) model surpassed many of the baseline models, as emoji's provide emotional context which helps in the recognition of sarcasm. The only drawback for this approach is that use of emoji's is limited to online text messaging.

The researcher developed a machine learning-based model that identifies sentiment and sarcasm using n-gram features. The research indicates that enhancing classification accuracy can be achieved by combining sarcasm characteristics with the polarity of sentiment. However, complex patterns in sarcasm are difficult for typical machine learning methods to handle [8]. Authors introduce a hierarchical fusion model designed for detecting sarcasm in tweets by combining text, images, and image attribute features. For future research, they plan to include additional modalities like audio and use common-sense knowledge to enhance model performance further [9].

The researcher developed a framework for identifying sarcasm by applying machine learning and deep learning models to a large dataset containing 1.3 million social media comments. They compared BiLSTM and BERT-based models with traditional classifiers after performing natural language processing-based pre-processing. The study offers a detailed comparison of these models using a large-scale dataset [10].

In order to eliminate the noise found in hashtag-based Twitter datasets, the researcher proposed a hybrid neural network for detecting sarcasm. This model uses a high-quality dataset consisting of both sarcastic and genuine news articles [11].The researcher addressed a challenging and little-studied issue in text-based sarcasm analysis by introducing a method for detecting sarcasm in tweets without using the #sarcasm hashtag. The research emphasizes the importance of contextual understanding in identifying sarcasm, especially when there are no clear signs of it [12].The author introduced sarcasm detection models that combine deep learning methods with traditional classifiers that use detailed features. They developed an SVM model that relies on punctuation, sentiment, and meaning, and it showed better performance compared to other approaches [13].To improve sentiment analysis in online reviews by identifying sentiment incongruity within sentences, the author proposed a sarcasm detection approach. They used Amazon review data and classified each sentence as positive or negative through dependency parsing and part-of-speech-based phrase segmentation [14].

The authors looked at 30 studies published from 2019 to 2022 as part of their detailed review of the existing literature on detecting sarcasm in text from social networks. They analyzed the methods, databases, and evaluation measures used in these studies [15]. To accurately evaluate online comments, author developed a sarcasm detection framework that includes emotion recognition. Their approach uses sentiment scoring along with algorithms that detect sarcasm based on hashtags, emoticons, and interjections [16]. A machine learning approach for detecting sarcasm in tweets was introduced by the researcher, focusing on the use of emoji's and textual indicators such as irony and hyperbole. By recognizing the subtle ways sarcasm is expressed in social media messages, their approach enhances the accuracy of sentiment analysis [17].

The researcher's used a multimedia corpus of sarcastic Russian speech to study automatic verbal irony detection using neural networks. They applied convolutional neural networks to analyze facial expressions and used Wav2Vec 2.0 to extract acoustic features [18].The authors used a multimedia dataset containing sarcastic Russian speech to explore the automatic detection of verbal irony through neural networks. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) were applied in their study to analyze facial expressions

and made use of used Wav2Vec 2.0 for the extraction of acoustic features from audio signals [19].

CNN and pre-trained transformers to integrate information related to context emotion and sentiment, were used for the detection of sarcasm by the researchers [20]. In remote communication environments the authors explored speech emotion recognition (SER) using traditional machine learning techniques [21].

An Automatic Face Analysis system was developed by Tian et al. This system focused on the detection of facial Action Units (AUs) as defined by the Facial Action Coding System (FACS), instead of recognizing basic facial expressions [22]. Combination of sentiment analysis and identification of facial emotion in order to overcome the ambiguity of sarcastic expression using multimodal approach was proposed by the researchers [23]. The identification of seven basic emotional states: neutral, anger, fear, happiness, sadness, surprise and disgust were

focused on by the researcher using an emotion recognition approach which was based on facial expression [24].

A detailed overview survey of sentiment analysis and detection of sarcasm within the area of machine learning and natural language processing was presented by the authors. The implicit nature of sarcasm, short-text constraints, contextual dependence, and issues related to multilingual and low-resource languages which were the key challenges were identified in this study [25]. With the aim of improving sarcasm on twitter, the authors presented a method that made use of context, rather than relying on individual tweets. As sarcasm mostly means the opposite of what is actually being said it is necessary to take into account the surrounding context [26].

The short comings of the traditional content-based approaches were addressed by the authors, who introduced a context-aware method for the detection of sarcasm [27].

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Sarcasm Detection Literature

Sr. No.	Author(s)	Year	Modality	Method / Model	Dataset	Key Contribution
1	Tingre et al.	2024	Text + Emoji's	ML sentiment-shift model	Twitter	Emoji-based sarcasm detection
2	Kochetkova et al.	2024	Audio + Video	CNN + Wav2Vec 2.0	Russian multimodal	Acoustic + facial cues improve irony detection
3	Yacoub et al.	2024	Text	Survey	Multiple datasets	Summarizes challenges & trends
4	Farabi et al.	2024	Multimodal	Survey	Multiple public datasets	Highlights multimodal advantage
5	Vitmana et al.	2023	Text	CNN + Transformers	SARC (movies, tech), IAC-V2, Twitter	Emotion-aware context improves sarcasm detection
6	Šandor & Babić	2023	Text	BiLSTM, BERT	1.3M online comments	Large-scale comparison
7	Alqahtani et al.	2023	Text	Systematic review	30 studies	Identifies trends and gaps
8	Vitmana et al.	2023	Text	CNN + Transformers	SARC, IAC-V2, Twitter	State-of-the-art performance
9	Saini et al.	2023	Audio/Text/Video	MNB, LR, LSVM	Multimodal datasets	Strong ML baseline for SER
10	Nayel et al.	2021	Text	ML with n-grams	Arabic datasets	Combines sentiment & sarcasm features
11	Bagate & Suguna	2021	Text	Ensemble ML + DL	Twitter (no hashtag)	Sarcasm detection without hashtags
12	Hiremath & Patil	2021	Visual	CNN on cognitive visual features	Visual sarcasm dataset	Visual cues for sarcasm
13	Kedar et al.	2021	Text + Face	CNN + sentiment analysis	Facial emotion dataset	Emotion-sentiment incongruity modelling
14	Eke et al.	2021	Text	BiLSTM + BERT hybrid	Twitter, IAC-V2	Contextual feature fusion
15	Potamias et al.	2020	Text	Transformer	Twitter & benchmark datasets;	Captures long-range dependencies
16	Kumar et al.	2020	Text	MHA-BiLSTM, SVM	Social media comments	Attention improves context modelling
17	Subramanian et al.	2019	Text + Emoji's	ESD model	Twitter; Accuracy	Emojis enhance sarcasm cues
18	Cai et al.	2019	Text + Image	Hierarchical fusion	Multimodal Twitter dataset	Multimodal fusion boosts performance
19	Misra & Arora (2019)	2019	Text	Hybrid NN + Attention	News sarcasm dataset	Improved interpretability
20	Rendalkar & Chandankhede	2018	Text	Emotion & sentiment lexicons	Online comments	Emotion detection aids sarcasm
21	Suzuki et al.	2017	Text	POS & dependency parsing	Amazon reviews	Improves sentiment analysis
22	Tarnowski et al.	2017	Visual	k-NN, MLP	Kinect 3D facial data	High lab emotion recognition accuracy
23	Bouazizi & Ohtsuki (2016)	2016	Text	Pattern-based rules	Twitter; Precision, Recall	Linguistic patterns for sarcasm
24	Wang et al.	2015	Text	Context-based SVM-HMM	Twitter conversation	Context improves detection
25	Tian et al.	2001	Visual	AU-based analysis	FACS	FACS-coded image sequences

Twitter is the predominant source for the majority of the existing research that is based on text-centric datasets the performance has mostly been evaluated using Accuracy and F1-score. Though improved results have been shown with the use of multimodal approach, the explicit use of facial Action Unit analysis remains largely unexplored. This research gap draws attention to the fact that is a significant opportunity to study the incorporation of AU-based facial expression modelling into the frameworks of sarcasm detection.

Fig: comparative analysis

4. Conclusion:

Text and deep learning methods which have proved to work better than the traditional machine learning has been the focus on most of the existing studies. The combination of text along with other data, i.e. a multimodal approach has shown an improvement in the results, but the needs datasets which are complex. The detection of sarcasm from facial expressions still remains largely unexplored and the availability of datasets and models for this are minimal. Thus the use of facial expressions and deep learning to further improve the recognition of sarcasm in the real world human computer interaction gives one a scope for future studies.

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